

EVIDENCE OF urKREEP ASSIMILATION IN NWA 16286 USING CHLORINE ISOTOPES. M. Boruah^{1*}, M. Anand¹, R. Tartèse², J. F. Snape², A. Stephant³, X. Zhao¹, I. Buisman⁴, L.F. White¹, I. Franchi¹. ¹School of Physical Sciences, The Open University, UK, ²Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, The University of Manchester, UK, ³Instituto di Astrofisica e Planetologia Spaziali (INAF), Rome, Italy, ⁴Department of Earth Sciences, University of Cambridge, UK. *Corresponding Author: moni.boruah@open.ac.uk

Introduction: Lunar samples are known to exhibit a wide range of chlorine (Cl) isotope composition ($\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$), ranging from -4% to $+81\%$ [1; 2]. Previous studies have proposed anhydrous degassing of metal chlorides [3], mixing of Cl-poor and Cl-rich reservoirs [4] and vapour induced metasomatism [5] to address this large spread. However, most of these hypotheses are based on studies conducted on apatite, a late-stage mineral which forms after the crystallisation of 90-95% of the primary basaltic magma. As a result, it is difficult to determine whether the mechanisms responsible for elevated $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ are fingerprints of melts experiencing early differentiation or late-stage interactions. Melt inclusion (MI) trapped in early-formed minerals, on the other hand, can potentially capture the initial volatile fingerprint of the parent magma. Despite this potential, Cl isotope studies from MIs have been reported from only a few lunar basalts [6]. In particular, the temporal evolution of Cl isotopes between melt generation and solidification remains largely unexplored. Here we present the Cl abundances and isotope compositions from olivine-hosted melt inclusions (OHMI) and apatite in a lunar meteorite, Northwest Africa (NWA) 16286.

Sample: NWA 16286 is a crystalline basaltic meteorite found in Ouargla, Algeria [7]. It is characterised as a high K_2O and intermediate TiO_2 mare basalt with large olivine phenocrysts, possibly from the Procellarum KREEP Terrain. The crystallisation age of the sample is reported as 2201 ± 13 Ma [8], making it the youngest lunar basaltic meteorite known so far.

Analytical methods: Apatite grains and OHMI were identified using a TESCAN Clara scanning electron microscope at the Open University (OU), UK. A beam condition of 1 nA and 20 keV, at a working distance of 10 mm, was used for the analysis.

Cl abundance and isotopic composition in both apatite and OHMI were measured using CAMECA Nanoscale Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (NanoSIMS) 50L ion microprobe in imaging mode at OU, following the protocol modified after [6]. For apatite, pre-sputtering was done for 3 minutes over $12 \times 12 \mu\text{m}$ areas using a 100 pA Cs^+ beam to remove any surface contamination, followed by analysis with a 20 pA primary Cs^+ beam with a diameter of 300 nm over $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ areas. Secondary ions of $^{16}\text{O}^1\text{H}$, ^{18}O , ^{19}F , ^{35}Cl , ^{37}Cl and $^{40}\text{Ca}^{16}\text{O}$ were imaged simultaneously on electron multipliers (EM) with a mass resolving power (MRP) of ~ 7000 . Each analysis ran for 15 minutes. Terrestrial apatite standards AP004, AP005, and AP018 [9] were used to generate calibration curves to estimate Cl abundance; however, only

AP004 was used to correct instrumental mass fractionation in the measured $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ ratio; $\delta^{37}\text{Cl} = ((^{37}\text{Cl}/^{35}\text{Cl})_{\text{sample}} / (^{37}\text{Cl}/^{35}\text{Cl})_{\text{SMOC}} - 1) \times 1000$ and SMOC = standard mean ocean chloride value [10].

Figure 1: Backscattered electron (BSE) image of apatite (a, b) and OHMI (c, d) in NWA 16286. Ol=Olivine, Px= Pyroxene, Pl=Plagioclase, Ilm=ilmenite, Cr=Chromite, Ap=Apatite, and K-rich Gl=K-rich glass.

In case of OHMI, pre-sputtering was done for 5-10 minutes using a 300 pA Cs^+ beam over $15 \times 15 \mu\text{m}$ areas, followed by analysis with a 100 pA Cs^+ beam over $12 \times 12 \mu\text{m}$ areas. Secondary ions collected on EM were ^{12}C , ^{18}O , ^{30}Si , ^{35}Cl , ^{37}Cl and $^{27}\text{Al}^{16}\text{O}$. Each analysis ran for 30 minutes. Basaltic glass standards SR2-DR04 and MD57-D9-1 [11] were used to generate the calibration curve for estimating the Cl abundance, and IMF corrections were done using SR2-DR04. The measured Cl abundances were also corrected for post-entrapment crystallisation (PEC) using Petrolog 3 [12]. In both cases, data were processed using the L'IMAGE software developed by Larry Nittler, Carnegie Institute of Washington, following the procedure of [6]. The 2σ uncertainties of $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ were calculated by combining the external uncertainties from the standards and internal counting statistics from each unknown measurement, while the 2σ uncertainties of the Cl abundances were estimated by combining the uncertainty of the slope in the calibrations and analytical uncertainty of each analysis.

Results: Eight apatite grains were analysed in this study. They are irregular in shape, less than $25 \mu\text{m}$ in the longest dimension, and mostly found in the mesostasis regions between main mineral phases (Fig. 1). The measured Cl abundance ranges from $1028 \pm 79 \mu\text{g/g}$ to $5269 \pm 405 \mu\text{g/g}$, and $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ values range from $22.2 \pm 1.5\%$ to $30.2 \pm 2.5\%$ (Fig. 2). No apparent correlation is observed between the Cl abundance and isotope composition.

Ten OHMI were targeted for analysis. They are round to irregular in shape, about $30\text{-}100 \mu\text{m}$ in size. They are highly recrystallised and are often associated

with chromite (**Fig. 1**). The measured Cl abundances range from $92 \pm 17 \mu\text{g/g}$ to $239 \pm 44 \mu\text{g/g}$. Following PEC correction, the abundance ranges from $6.5 \pm 1.2 \mu\text{g/g}$ to $18.4 \pm 3.3 \mu\text{g/g}$. The $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ values of OHMI range from $-0.4 \pm 2.2 \text{‰}$ to $7.7 \pm 2.0 \text{‰}$ and are not correlated with Cl abundances (**Fig. 2**).

Figure 2: $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ (‰) versus Cl content ($\mu\text{g/g}$) of apatite and OHMI (PEC corrected) in NWA 16286, in comparison to Apollo OHMI and apatite [6]. Error bars = 2σ uncertainties. The light orange band represents Mg-suite rocks $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}_{\text{apatites}}$, dotted band represents KREEP-rich and VHK basalts, and pink band represents mare basalts [13].

Discussions: Magmatic degassing of metal chlorides has been previously proposed to explain Cl isotopic fractionation in lunar basalts [1]. We used Rayleigh distillation fractionation factors for NaCl , HCl and ZnCl_2 , which showed that for an initial $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ of 3.4‰ (average $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}_{\text{OHMI}}$), it would take 56 to $> 96 \%$ losses of Cl via degassing to reach the average $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ -apatite. Considering Cl is incompatible in silicates, using $D_{\text{ap/melt}}$ of 1-5 [14], 97.4 to 99.5% fractional crystallisation would be needed before the onset of apatite crystallisation to account for the average $2392 \mu\text{g/g}$ Cl in apatite. This suggests that starting from an even lighter $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ value to account for Cl loss via degassing before melt entrapment in olivine would need more extensive degassing and, thus, crystallisation to be consistent with the observed apatite Cl- $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ values.

The relationship between bulk rock incompatible trace element (ITE) ratios and $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ in apatites has been previously employed to propose mixing of two distinct Cl reservoirs in the lunar interior: a Cl-poor reservoir with $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ values like Earth's mantle and a Cl-rich reservoir with elevated $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ values, like urKREEP [4] (where urKREEP represents the last melt dregs enriched in ITE such as K, REE, P, at the end of the lunar magma ocean crystallisation). When plotted against the bulk La/Sm ratio, apatite $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ in NWA 16286 roughly follows the positive trend defined by mare basalts and KREEP-rich rocks, whilst the OHMI fall well below it (**Fig. 3**), suggesting assimilation of KREEP-derived material after entrapment of the melt inclusions during magma ascent. To further constrain the timing and magnitude of urKREEP assimilation, we carried out mixing calculations following [4]. These calculations show that a

Cl-rich urKREEP assimilation is required to account for the values measured in apatite. Additionally, if the assimilation happens after $>50\%$ crystallisation, it is unlikely to drive the $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ of the final melt to values measured in apatite. This implies that contamination happened soon after the entrapment of melt in the olivine.

Figure 3: Apatite and OHMI $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ values vs. bulk rock La/Sm for NWA 16286 and a range of lunar products. Error bars= 2SD . The brown line represents the line of best fit representing the mixing trend estimated in [15].

Conclusions: Cl abundance and isotope compositions obtained in OHMI and apatite in NWA 16286 reveal that magmatic degassing of Cl-bearing species after OHMI entrapment, followed by extensive crystallisation before apatite formation, could explain the apatite Cl- $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ systematics. Equally, mixing models suggest that assimilation of a Cl-rich urKREEP component soon after the entrapment of OHMI can largely account for the observed Cl- $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ systematics. This also demonstrates that the mixing model of two Cl reservoirs can be resolved in a single lunar basalt. Interestingly, the lowest $\delta^{37}\text{Cl}$ value measured in this study indicates close similarities between the lunar and terrestrial interiors.

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